

Mechanism and Apparent Energy of Activation of B-Z Reaction with Mannose and Bromate in Presence of one Equivalent Oxidant in Aqueous Medium

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The oscillatory chemical reactions (mainly Belousov¹-Zhabotinskii(B-Z) reaction) have been studied by different workers using different substrates, both inorganic and organic. The present work deals with the determination of apparent energy of activation and possible mechanism of the reaction system² containing BrO_3^- , H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 , mannose and Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The results of the oscillatory characters of the reaction systems are presented in Table 1. The apparent energy of activation for the overall process was calculated from the slope of linear plot of $\log t_i$ vs $1/T$ (not shown) on the basis that the rate of oscillation is taken to be a measure of the rate of the reaction for the period when the oscillations are taking place.

TABLE 1— H_2SO_4 - H_3PO_4 , BrO_3^- , Ce^{III} AND Mn^{II} SYSTEMS

Temp. (I) T (K)	1/T 10^{-3}	Time of initiation t_i (s)	$\log 1/t_i$	Time period t (s)	$\log 1/t$	Ampli- tude (mV)
Ce ^{III} system :						
298	3.356	800	-2.903 1	100	-2.000 0	12
302	3.311	528	-2.722 6	61	-1.785 3	10
306	3.270	304	-2.482 9	45	-1.653 2	7
310	3.229	201	-2.301 0	24	-1.380 2	3
Mn ^{II} system :						
298	3.350	275	-2.439 9	95	-1.977 7	8
302	3.311	180	-2.255 3	59	-1.770 9	6
306	3.270	102	-2.008 6	42	-1.623 2	4
310	3.229	70	-1.845 1	22	-1.342 4	1

It was noted in each case that the rise in potential corresponds to the rise in Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} and the decrease in potential due to generation of Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} . Maximum rise in potential occurred when solution acquired a faint yellow characteristic of Ce^{IV} ion and minimum potential when the solution was colourless due to presence of Ce^{III} ion in excess. Similarly, the solution acquired pink colour characteristic of Mn^{III} ion when the potential was maximum and the solution was colourless due to Mn^{II} ion when the potential was minimum. The process of oxidation involves the production of Br_2 due to the oxidation of mannose by bromate.

Effect of temperature : The effect of increasing temperature on the oscillation rate shows that due to increase in temperature the time-period for a single oscillation is decreased. From the nature of the curve in the range of 298–309 K, it seems that increase in frequency with increase in temperature is more or less exponential, the increase at the lower temperature region being much more than in the higher temperature regions. It is, therefore, clear that at higher temperature the oscillation will practically vanish.

If the rate of oscillation is taken to be the measure of the rate of reaction for the period when oscillations are taking place, the Arrhenius plots ($\log_{10} k$ against $1/T$), the values of energy of activation calculated from empirical rate equation are : mannose- BrO_3^- - Ce^{III} , 91.96 ; mannose- BrO_3^- - Mn^{II} , 87.78 kJ mol⁻¹.

Mechanism : The investigation might throw some light on the mechanism with respect to nature of bond-making and -breaking involved in oscillation. Noyes³ made a detailed investigation of the reaction between malonic acid, BrO_3^- and Ce^{III} ions and gave the mechanism of oscillation, which can be satisfactorily applied in this case.

The mannose is first oxidised by Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} ion giving Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} ions. We have studied this reaction independently and found that the reactions occur as follows :

The production of Ce^{III} and Mn^{II} causes the potentials to fall in the beginning and after some time they start reacting with BrO_3^- autocatalytically producing bromine,

Simultaneously, BrO_3^- also oxidised mannose to uronic acid by producing HOBr,

Again, HOBr produced Br₂ as follows :

The third step is

The bromide ion produced inhibits the Ce^{III}-BrO₃⁻ or Mn^{II}-BrO₃⁻ reaction so the formation of Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} is stopped. By this time sufficient Ce^{IV} or Mn^{III} has accumulated in the system to react with mannose and get reduced to Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} ion. In this way the periodic fluctuation of [Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III}] or [Mn^{III}/Mn^{II}] ratio goes on.

Side by side, the tartaric acid produced is oxidised by BrO₃⁻ giving HBrO₂,

Such reaction takes place only at a slight by higher temperature. In this case we have noticed that oscillations start after a long induction period and have long life. The oscillations occurred due to formation of oxalic acid from tartaric acid, an oxidation product of mannose.

Experimental

The oscillations in the concentration of Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} or Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} were recorded using X-t recorder. Platinum was employed as indicator electrode and saturated calomel used as the reference electrode together with (saturated KNO₃) salt-bridge having a sintered silica disc at the end dipping in the reaction mixture. All the constituents except one

(mannose solution) were placed in a glass cell provided with a jacket through which preconditioned water was passed for studies at various temperatures. The reaction mixture was thoroughly stirred with a magnetic stirrer. When the temperature of the reaction mixture become constant ($\pm 0.1^\circ$), the mannose solution thermostated at the same temperature was instantly transferred to the cell. The measurements were then made at 25, 29, 33 and 37° for Mn^{II} and Ce^{III}.

The oscillatory characters of each reaction system were followed by (i) indicator method and (ii) electrometric method. The composition of reaction mixture was as follows: H₂SO₄ (1.5*N*), H₃PO₄ (1.5*N*), BrO₃⁻ (0.063*M*), Ce^{III} (0.001*M*)/Mn^{II} (0.0012 *M*) and mannose (0.004*M*).

Indicator method: In this method, before adding the fourth reactant ferroin indicator (2–3 drops) was added in the case of Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III}. There is no need of ferroin in the case of Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} system. After some time the colour of the solution started showing periodic oscillations from blue to red in the case of Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} and colourless to pink in the case of Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} in the reacting solution. These periodic changes in colour were due to oscillation of the Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} or Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} ratio around a mean value. This method, however, could not be applicable at higher temperature as the indicator tended to decompose.

Electrometric method: The fluctuation in the [Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III}] or [Mn^{III}/Mn^{II}] ratio against time was recorded electrometrically by inserting Pt-fol (1 cm²) sealed in a glass tube.

References

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